

Sound Velocity from Flory's Statistical Theory and Some Thermodynamic Excess Functions for Binary Mixtures of Isooctane with Benzene and with Toluene

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Flory's statistical theory has been extended to evaluate sound velocity for the binary liquid mixtures of isooctane + benzene and isooctane + toluene at 298.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K. The agreement between the theoretical and calculated sound velocity is good. The values of excess adiabatic and isothermal compressibilities, and excess Gruneisen parameter have also been evaluated and these excess functions have been discussed in terms of inter-molecular interactions. The free volume evaluated using sound velocity has been found to be an important tool to predict the interaction in liquid mixtures.

SEVERAL attempts¹⁻¹³ have been made to test Flory's statistical theory^{13,14} for binary liquid mixtures in the light of thermodynamic excess functions. Very recently Nath and Dubey¹⁵ have evaluated excess volume and excess free energy for different binary mixtures using Flory's theory. But the attempts to evaluate sound velocity using reduced and characteristic parameters of Flory's equation are rare.

Recently Pandey *et al.*¹⁶⁻²⁰ have evaluated sound velocity using Auerbach²¹ relation.

In the present paper we have evaluated sound velocity of the title binaries and the theoretical results have been compared with experimental findings. Some thermodynamic excess functions and free volume have also been evaluated and the result has been discussed in terms of inter-molecular interaction.

Theoretical :

Sound velocity (C) and the surface tension (σ) are related by Auerbach²¹ relation as

$$C = \left(\frac{\sigma}{6.3 \times 10^{-4} \times \rho} \right)^{2/3} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density.

According to Flory's statistical theory^{13,14}, the surface tension is expressed as

$$\sigma = \sigma^* \bar{\sigma}(\bar{V}) \quad (2)$$

where σ^* and $\bar{\sigma}(\bar{V})$ are the characteristic surface tension and reduced surface tension, respectively. Patterson and Rastogi²², in their extension of the corresponding state theory to deal with the surface tension, used the reduction parameter as

$$\sigma^* = K^{1/3} P^{2/3} T^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

where, K is Boltzmann constant, and P* and T* are the characteristic pressure and characteristic

temperature, respectively. Starting from the work of Prigogine and Saraga²³, they also derived a reduced surface tension equation as

$$\bar{\sigma}(\bar{V}) = M \bar{V}^{-5/3} - \frac{\bar{V}^{1/3} - 1}{\bar{V}^2} \ln \frac{\bar{V}^{1/3} - 0.5}{\bar{V}^{1/3} - 1} \quad (4)$$

where, $\bar{V}$ ($\bar{V} = V/V^*$, where V^* is characteristic volume) is reduced volume and M is the fraction of nearest neighbours which a molecule loses on moving from the bulk of the liquid to the surface. Its most suitable value has been found to be 0.29.

The excess isothermal compressibility of the liquid mixtures has been evaluated by the following equations^{13,14}.

$$\beta_T^E = \frac{3\bar{V}^2(\bar{V}^{1/3} - 1)}{P^*[1 - 3(\bar{V}^{1/3} - 1)]} - \frac{1}{\bar{V}} [\psi_1 V_1 \beta_{T(1)} + \psi_2 V_2 \beta_{T(2)}] \quad (5)$$

The adiabatic compressibility, which is given by $\beta_g = C^{-2} \rho^{-1}$, has been used to obtain excess adiabatic compressibility by the relation,

$$\beta_g^E = \beta_{g(m)} - [\psi_1 \beta_{g(1)} + \psi_2 \beta_{g(2)}] \quad (6)$$

In equation (6), ψ_1 and ψ_2 are segment fraction and are expressed as

$$\psi_2 = 1 - \psi_1 = \frac{x_2}{x_2 + x_1 (\bar{V}_1^*/\bar{V}_2^*)} \quad (7)$$

where, x_1 , x_2 and $\bar{V}_1^*$, $\bar{V}_2^*$ are mole fractions and characteristic volumes of components 1 and 2, respectively.

The expression for Gruneisen parameter, Γ can be expressed as

$$\Gamma = \frac{C^2 \alpha}{C_p} = \frac{\gamma - 1}{T \cdot \alpha} \quad (8)$$

where, α , γ and C are, respectively, the thermal expansion coefficient, heat capacities ratio and

TABLE 1—SOUND VELOCITY AND RELATED PARAMETERS EVALUATED FROM FLORY THEORY AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp K	x_1	σ^* dyn cm ⁻¹	$\frac{\sigma(\bar{v})}{10^5}$	σ dyn cm ⁻¹	C_{calcd} ms ⁻¹	C_{exptl} ms ⁻¹	$\frac{\Delta C}{C}$ %
Isooctane + Benzene							
298.15	1.0000	195.8	8979	17.57	1181.7	1082.2	8.43
	0.7591	205.8	8877	18.27	1183.8	1108.7	6.33
	0.4971	220.4	8799	19.39	1190.6	1144.2	3.86
	0.2490	240.3	8773	21.08	1207.0	1202.1	0.41
	0.0000	269.8	8884	23.96	1238.8	1297.8	-4.76
313.15	1.0000	191.7	8457	16.39	1139.4	1020.0	10.50
	0.7591	203.1	8378	17.02	1143.2	1044.6	8.62
	0.4971	217.1	8311	18.11	1161.8	1077.2	6.48
	0.2490	237.5	8299	19.71	1167.8	1195.3	2.78
	0.0000	267.0	8391	22.40	1199.0	1229.4	-2.50
323.15	1.0000	190.7	9160	15.54	1111.7	979.2	11.93
	0.7591	200.7	8073	16.20	1116.6	1001.0	10.36
	0.4971	215.8	8010	17.29	1126.3	1032.7	8.34
	0.2491	233.7	7989	18.81	1141.5	1090.8	4.46
	0.0000	262.8	8088	21.41	1173.2	1184.0	-0.91
Isooctane + Toluene							
298.15	1.0000	195.8	8979	17.57	1181.7	1082.2	8.43
	0.7400	205.1	9091	18.64	1192.5	1117.4	6.30
	0.4970	217.4	9222	20.05	1211.3	1165.5	3.78
	0.2563	233.5	9398	21.94	1237.6	1223.6	1.13
	0.0000	255.5	9683	24.69	1274.7	1304.2	2.81
313.15	1.0000	191.7	8457	16.33	1139.4	1020.0	10.50
	0.7400	202.4	8587	17.51	1157.7	1054.4	8.92
	0.4970	215.0	8740	18.93	1179.6	1101.8	6.67
	0.2563	231.0	8942	20.80	1208.3	1160.7	3.93
	0.0000	253.2	9244	23.57	1249.5	1240.4	0.72
323.15	1.0000	190.7	8150	15.54	1111.7	979.2	11.93
	0.7400	200.0	8289	16.70	1131.7	1013.6	10.44
	0.4970	212.7	8450	18.10	1154.4	1059.2	8.24
	0.2563	228.7	8663	19.95	1184.7	1119.0	5.54
	0.0000	251.0	8980	22.71	1228.6	1198.0	2.49

velocity of sound. The excess Gruneisen parameter, Γ^E is calculated using the relation,

$$\Gamma^E = \Gamma_{m_{12}} - \sum_{i=1}^2 x_i \Gamma_i \quad (9)$$

where, $\Gamma_{m_{12}}$ is the pseudo Gruneisen parameter of the mixture, x_i the mole fractions and Γ_i the Gruneisen parameter of the pure components i ($i=1,2$).

The free volume (V_f) is evaluated by the relation of Eyring *et al.*²⁴,

$$V_f = V \left[\frac{V_g}{V_L} \right]^8 \quad (10)$$

where, V_g and V_L are the sound velocity in the gas and liquid phase, respectively, and V the molar volume.

Results and Discussion

The values of characteristic and reduced surface tension evaluated in the light of equations (3) and (4) are enlisted in Table 1. The sound velocity

evaluated using these parameters has been compared with the experimental values in Table 1, at different temperatures for the systems, isooctane+benzene and isooctane+toluene. The necessary data for these calculations have been taken from the measurements made by Subrahmanyam *et al.*²⁵. The perusal of Table 1 indicates that the agreement between the calculated and experimental sound velocities is fairly good. At all the three temperatures studied, the percentage deviation of sound velocity for the system isooctane+benzene, decreases with the decrease in the concentration of isooctane and becomes negative for pure benzene component. For the system isooctane+toluene, the percentage deviation also decreases with increase in toluene concentration but the deviation is not negative for pure toluene component. It is to be pointed out that in both the systems, the percentage deviation increases with temperature. Since M is the fractional decrease in the number of neighbours of a cell in the surface phase as compared to the bulk phase, it should have values which vary with temperature. Patterson and Rastogi²² have suggested a range values from 0.25 to 0.29. Deviations can be further minimised by adopting suitable value for M .

The positive deviation for toluene as compared to benzene may be attributed to its larger molar volume.

The values of the quantity β_s^E , β_T^E , Γ^E and free volume for the title binaries at 298.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K are given in Table 2. Table 2 indicates that for both the systems at all the temperatures, the values of excess functions which are indications for inter-molecular interactions in the systems studied, are negative. At all the three temperatures, the negative values of β_s^E and β_T^E increase with decrease in the concentration of isooctane which shows increasing trend of interaction.

The excess Gruneisen parameter, included in Table 2, varies with temperature and composition of the mixture and hence, $\Gamma^E = \Gamma^E(X)$. For the system isooctane+benzene the negative magnitude of Γ^E varies with the concentration of isooctane and is maximum at equimolar composition. This is an indication of association in the mixture. The values of Γ^E for the system isooctane+toluene is comparatively lower in magnitude. Thus, the negative magnitude of Γ^E follows the sequence, benzene > toluene.

Free volume of the liquid, the void space not occupied by rigid molecular volumes, has been used as an important tool to predict the interaction in the liquid mixtures by several workers²⁸⁻²⁹. Recently, Pandey *et al.*³⁰ have evaluated free volume of water+alcohol systems using sound velocity data.

In the present communication the free volume evaluated by equation (10) is given in Table 2. For both the systems the values of free volume decrease with the decrease in concentration of the first component. This continuous decrease in free volume indicates weak molecular interaction in the systems.

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TABLE 2—EXCESS ADIABATIC COMPRESSIBILITY (β_s^E), EXCESS ISOTHERMAL COMPRESSIBILITY (β_T^E), EXCESS GRUNEISEN PARAMETER (Γ^E) AND FREE VOLUME AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. K	x_1	β_s^E G Pa ⁻¹	β_T^E G Pa ⁻¹	Γ^E	V_f cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Isooctane + Benzene					
298.15	0.7591	-0.0145	-0.0024	-0.0595	0.566
	0.4971	-0.0240	-0.0071	-0.1207	0.524
	0.2490	-0.0269	-0.0130	-0.0652	0.481
313.15	0.7591	-0.0145	-0.0053	-0.0887	0.716
	0.4971	-0.0218	-0.0123	-0.1256	0.679
	0.2490	-0.0302	-0.0158	-0.0449	0.571
323.15	0.7591	-0.0155	-0.0069	-0.0867	0.858
	0.4971	-0.0174	-0.0184	-0.1318	0.807
	0.2490	-0.0366	-0.0175	-0.0797	0.729
Isooctane + Toluene					
298.15	0.7400	-0.0255	-0.0313	-0.0330	0.529
	0.4970	-0.0477	-0.0452	-0.0306	0.471
	0.2563	-0.0442	-0.0394	-0.0092	0.408
313.15	0.7400	-0.0275	-0.0369	-0.0440	0.681
	0.4970	-0.0491	-0.0552	-0.0484	0.598
	0.2563	-0.0516	-0.0495	-0.0235	0.512
323.15	0.7400	-0.0332	-0.0487	-0.0384	0.808
	0.4970	-0.0590	-0.0725	-0.0225	0.714
	0.2563	-0.0622	-0.0645	-0.0125	0.608